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PREVALENCE OF PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE ABUSE IN A UNIVERSITY COMMUNITY: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

A study carried out by The Centre for Counselling and Career Development of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, on behalf of the Committee on War against Substance Abuse and Trafficking on Campus

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Abstract

This study examined the prevalence of substance abuse in a University Community; involving 394 participants that were selected using multi-staged sampling method; from four departments in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. They comprised of 278 students, and 116 staff. Their ages ranged from 18 to 62 years; with a mean age of 24, and standard deviation of 7. Two instruments were used for data collection, they are: Campus Awareness of Psychoactive Substance Abuse Questionnaire (CAPSAQ), and Drug abuse screening test (DAST). This study was a cross-section survey, and descriptive (percentage), and two-way ANOVA were adopted as the statistical tools for data analysis. The descriptive statistics revealed that 5.1% of the total participants abuse drug. It was also showed that among the male's participants, 6% abuse drug; while 5.2% of the female's participants, abuse drug. The results also showed that 3.4% of the staff's participants abuse drug; while 6.1% of the students' participants abuse drug. On awareness of harm caused by drugs, 81% of the male's participants were well informed; while 62% of the female's participants were well informed. The analyses further revealed that among the drug peddlers on Campus, staff's involvement was rated as 13.9%, students' involvement as 33.8%; while outsiders constituted 52.3%. More so, the ANOVA statistics showed that there was no significant difference between males and females on substance abuse at $F(1,390)=.778, p>.05$. However, a significant difference was found between staff and students on substance abuse at $F(1,390)=5.617, p<.05$. Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommended among others, that there is need for the University management to step up on anti-drug policies in the University, and its' enforcement.

Keywords: prevalence, psychoactive substance, abuse, university, community

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Introduction

The knowledge that substance use disorder has become phenomenal across the globe, and the suspicion that it has crept into the university system necessitated this study; aimed at a cross-sectional assessment of awareness of different aspects of the issue of substance abuse, prevalence, and possible involvement of members of the University community as well as itinerants in the marketing of psychoactive substances in and around the University. More so, psychoactive substance use disorder has become a global phenomenon and mental health pandemic that has drawn multidisciplinary attention because of its physiological, psychological, social and forensic implications. Psychoactive substance abuse significantly alters the brain chemistry by which action they affect human functioning in negative ways. Such alteration places abusers in a state of dependence with strong craving, and withdrawal symptoms in absence of the psychoactive substance(s) of abuse. Hence, abusers do everything possible to obtain the drug(s) of abuse; even if it involves criminal behavior.

The obsessive and impulsive behaviour associated with drug abuse could be as a result of the neural changes in the brain of abusers and hyper stimulation of the reward pathways which drives abusers into reward seeking behaviour. Thus, making deliberate withdrawal from these psychoactive substances by abusers difficult, if not impossible, irrespective of obvious negative effects. This scenario becomes daunting when it involves members of the Ivory Tower: the

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University which is esteemed for positive developments, and designated for proffering solutions to societal problems. Indeed, students' involvement in substance abuse has been described as the most destructive practice because of its association with negative academic, and social outcomes; such as, poor academic grade, poor interpersonal interaction, cultism, and criminality. Thus, the need for a prevalence study becomes rather obvious; since without baseline information, meaningful intervention and programmes may be very difficult to actualize.

Like most addictive behaviour, psychoactive substance abuse starts from experimentation, and graduates to occasional use whether for recreation, for dealing with pain, or as a coping strategy against stress; but soon becomes more regular, leading to dependence. At that stage, the abuser can no longer function without intake of that particular psychoactive substance or similar ones at near regular intervals, leading to drug tolerance. Drug tolerance makes the abuser to increase initial doses that give the individual satisfaction overtime in order to have the same amount of euphoric feeling they used to have on the previous dose. Such tolerance gets tampered during treatment, and could lead to drug overdose in subsequent use of same amount prior to treatment. This could have a detrimental effect, including death in occasion of severe overdose. In Nigeria, adolescents and adults were identified to be the major groups involved in psychoactive substance abuse (Omigbodun & Babalola, 2004). Onifade (2010) stated that psychoactive substance abuse has been an issue of increasing health, social, and psychological importance; and Nigeria was considered the highest consumer of cannabis and amphetamines in Africa (Nigerian Epidemiological Network on Drug Use [NENDU], 2011).

WHO (2014) holds that substance abuse is one of the causes of juvenile delinquency, interpersonal violence, armed robbery, and road traffic accidents in many Societies; while many others abusers

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develop psychotic conditions, and some end up homeless. Obi-Nwosu et al. (2019) asserted that psychoactive substances abuse is an important public health challenge in the world today, and is a pandemic that needed to be tackled in every community. The negative implications of psychoactive substances include unwanted pregnancy, risk behaviour such as unprotected sex, criminal behaviour (in other to get money for psychoactive substance of choice), sexually transmitted infections, abortion, etc. Psychoactive substance abuse also leads to psychiatric conditions such as depression and anxiety, as well as suicide attempts, and actual suicide (Kahsay et al., 2019). According to Ochieng (2022), psychoactive substance abuse places students at risk of drug overdose as most times, they are the most vulnerable age group that constantly increases the doses of substances they consume; resulting to serious addiction as well as high risk situations that mostly affect their mental well-being.

Managing this alarming global pandemic has become imperative of its negative impact, mostly observed around adolescents and young adults, which translates to direct and indirect negative significant impact on the future, and development of the society since the youth of every society is their driving force. For instance, according to Peacock et al., (2018), the high rate of global consumption of Alcohol among individuals over the age of 15 years is 18.4%; daily tobacco smoking is 15.2%; while report on the prevalence of illicit drug consumption rate was over 3.8%. Report from UNODC (2018) indicating that individuals within the age range of 18 to 25 were most prone to substance abuse. Moreover, the most problematic part of it is that individuals within this age account for over 40% of the world population. Again, Olawole-Isaac et al., (2018) reported on rate of substance abuse in Sub-Saharan region as 41.6%, Central Africa was rated as 55.5%, East Africa as 48.99%, while West Africa accounted for 38.3%.

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Several observations have been made on the prevalence of psychoactive substances among academic populations; for instance, Mavhandu-Mudzusi and Asgedom (2016) rated their observation on psychoactive substance abuse among the University students in Ethiopia between 16.7% and 72%. According to Abate et al., (2021), the rate of substance abuse among high school students in Ethiopia is estimated at over 30%. Among African students population, the overall prevalence of substance abuse between the age of 16 and 25 years was 32.8% (Abata et al., 2021).

For the diagnosis of psychoactive substance use disorder to be made, at least two of the following signs and symptoms must be present:

1. Taking the substance in larger amounts or for longer than you are meant to.
2. Wanting to cut down or stop using the substance but not managing to.
3. Spending a lot of time getting, using, or recovering from use of the substance.
4. Cravings and urges to use the substance.
5. Not managing to do what you should at work, home, or school because of substance use.
6. Continuing to use, even when it causes problems in relationships.
7. Giving up important social, occupational, or recreational activities because of substance use.
8. Using substances again and again, even when it puts you in danger.
9. Continuing to use, even when you know you have a physical or psychological problem that could have been caused or made worse by the substance.
10. Needing more of the substance to get the effect you want (tolerance).

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11. Development of withdrawal symptoms, which can be relieved by taking more of the substance (DSM-V, 2013).

More so, using these symptoms, clinicians are at liberty to diagnose the severity of the disorder, based on the number of symptoms the person presents. Two or three symptoms indicate mild substance use disorder; four or five symptoms indicate moderate substance use disorder, and six or more symptoms indicate severe substance use disorder (McLellan, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

Psychoactive substance abuse poses treat to undergraduates, and can hamper the goal of studentship by interfering with their memory, influencing their association with delinquent peers, and development of physical and mental health conditions. More so, psychoactive substance abuse can result to drug overdose, which can have sudden and severe implication and can result to death (Ochieng, 2022). For some undergraduates, substance use is a coping strategy for stressors associated with studentship. Unfortunately, such maladaptive coping style can further complicate their lives (Obi-Nwosu et al. 2024; Onuoha et al., 2024). Furthermore, at the Centre for Counselling and Career Development, an increasing number of undergraduates report that stimulants and other substances help them to cope with undesirable situations and events; and that peer are major introducers of the substances

Since substance use is a maladaptive coping style to stressful situations, there is need to examine, and establish, with empirical evidence, the prevalence of psychoactive substance abuse in the University community. However, scholar such as Olawole-Isaac et al., (2018) and Olanrewaju et al. (2022) have investigated the prevalence of substance abuse involving African populations;

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furthermore, Adelekan (1992), and Ekwueme (2010), examined the prevalence of substance abuse among undergraduate students in Nigeria. However, no study to the best of the researchers' knowledge has examined the prevalence of psychoactive substance abuse among staff and students in any South Eastern university in Nigeria. Hence, the need for this study to close this gap.

Theories of drug abuse

Socio-Cultural model by Vygotsky (1978)

The theory poses that the cultural practices and standard of a society influences the behaviour of individuals from that culture. For instance, some behaviour could be common among people of one culture and not in the other, so, psychoactive substance use could be seen as a normal practice in one family or culture but as abnormal in another. Hence, there is high tendency that high rate of substance abuse will be recorded among the family or culture that sees substance abuse as a normal practice than those that sees it as a crime. Among university students, association with people or groups that abuse psychoactive substances will place non-abusive friends at risk of developing such maladaptive behaviour.

The Incentive Salience model

The Incentive Salience model posits links between sensitization of particular brain systems and motivation, which is distilled into the concept of drug craving. In this theory, the attribution of incentive salience to drug-related stimuli is increased by exposure to abused drugs (Robinson & Berridge 1999). Hence, Incentive Salience theory is attributable to drug use craving (Robinson &

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Berridge 2003). This theory explains the inability of university people, including students to stop or avoid psychoactive drug use even when they know that the substance is harmful to them; simply because they can no longer control the craving for the psychoactive substance.

Self-medication theory of addiction by Khantzian (1997)

The self-medication theory of addiction opined that individuals that abuse psychoactive drugs, or indulges in other addictive behaviour does not always involve in abuse because of the euphoric effect but to relieve dysphoria or those uncomfortable emotional state associated with abstinence. This theory explains reason why some university students continue to use psychoactive substances despite its negative effect on their academic performance as well as mental health; which is, to avoid the negative effect associated with the absence of such addictive substance in their body (withdrawal symptoms). Likewise, those that abuse as a result of peer pressure; hoping to avoid those negative emotion associated with the pressure from their friends that abuse psychoactive drugs.

Theoretical framework/Empirical review

Theoretically, this study was anchored on Incentive Salience model which posited that links exists between sensitization of a particular brain systems and motivation to use. This sensitization could be the resultant of the learnt maladaptive idea that drug use inhibits stressful emotions. This link explain the concept of drug craving. Hence, craving could be stimulated by the desire to cope with stressors within the university community; which is further complicated by the exposure to abused

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drugs. Thus explains the inability of university people, including students to stop or avoid psychoactive drug use even when they know its' negative impact on them; simply because of the availability of the drug of abuse within the university community that stimulating their desire to use, in occasions of life stressors, which are relatively unavoidable.

Several empirical studies among Nigerian populations have established the prevalence of psychoactive substance abuse among undergraduates in different localities such as: Adelekan (1992) that examined the prevalence of psychoactive substance use among undergraduates in Benin and reported 46.6%. Ekwueme (2010) found lifetime abuse of psychoactive substance among undergraduates in North Central Nigeria as 77%, while the researcher reported the rate among South East undergraduates between 3.2% and 37.4%. According to Babalola (2014), the prevalence psychoactive substance among undergraduates in Southwest Nigeria was between 58.4% and 65%, and over 15.4% were currently using psychoactive substance. Aguocho and Nwefoh (2021), stated that over 84.5 undergraduate student have abused psychoactive substance in their lifetime. Also, they observed alcohol to be the highest abused psychoactive substance among undergraduate students. They observed that over 82.5% of undergraduate students have abused alcohol in their lifetime while past 12-month abuse of alcohol was 61.1%. Life time abuse of psychoactive substance by male undergraduates was rated 86.1% while females' lifetime abuse of psychoactive substance was 83.4% (Aguocho & Nwefoh 2021). Furthermore, Olanrewaju et al. (2022) reported the prevalence of drug and other substance abuse among undergraduates in selected southwestern universities in Nigeria as 45.7%.

Research Questions

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Based on the forgoing, this study aimed at answering the following questions

1. What is the prevalence of psychoactive substance abuse on campus?
2. What is the prevalence by gender?
3. What percentage of staff and students in the University Community are likely into substance abuse?
4. What is the level of awareness of harm caused by psychoactive substance abuse in the University Community?
5. What percentage of drug peddlers in the University Community are student, staff or itinerants?
6. Will there be a significant difference between male and female on psychoactive substance abuse.
7. Will there be a significant difference between staff and students on psychoactive substance abuse.

This study aimed at understanding the incidents of psychoactive substance abuse in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. Hence, the outcome of the study will reveal the level of staff and students involvement with psychoactive substances.

Methods

Study Design

This is a survey research that utilized a cross-sectional research approach to ascertain the prevalence of psychoactive substance abuse; while descriptive (percentile), and two-way ANOVA statistics were adopted as the appropriate statistics for data analyses, using SPSS version 25.

Participants

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A total of 394 participants from Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka participated in this study. They comprise of 278 (70.6%) students and 116 (29.4%) staff. Among the 394, 201 (51%) were male while 193 (29.4) were female. 134 were married (43%) while 252 (64%) were single. 128 (32.5) were from Social Sciences, 90 (22.8) were from Bio Sciences, 106 (26.9) were from Education while 70 (17.8%) were from Management Sciences.

Instruments

Two instruments were used in this study for data collection they include: Campus Awareness of Psychoactive Substance Abuse Scale (CAPSAQ) and Drug Abuse Screening Test (DAST).

Campus Awareness of Psychoactive Substance Abuse Questionnaire (CAPSAQ)

CAPSAQ is a 14 item questionnaire, developed by CCCD, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, to measure awareness of harm, mode of distribution and involvement in psychoactive substance use/abuse in the University community. The scale was subjected to face and content validity through peer review, and came out as satisfactory. It is scored on a 4-point Likert scale format, ranging from 1 to 4: 1 indicates very little; while 4 indicates very much. Sample items for CAPSAQ include: "Estimate female student's abuse of psychoactive drug", "Rate itinerants' involvement in the sales and marketing of drugs around the campus", "Estimate how much you know about the harm caused by psychoactive substances abuse".

Reliability and Validity

CAPSAQ was subjected to face and content validity, through peer review of the initial 17 generated items, and 14 items came out as satisfactory. The 14 selected items were subjected to convergent validity by correlating them with DAST, and ($r = .67$) was found. Furthermore, the

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reliability coefficient of the selected CAPSAQ was tested, and a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of .88 was reported, indicating that the instrument is valid, and reliable.

Drug Abuse Screening Test (DAST)

Drug Abuse Screening Test (DAST) was developed by Skinner (1982) which is 28 items developed as a screening tool for people that have drug problem. The questionnaire has a response pattern of Yes or No; and question numbers 4, 5 and 7 are scored in the reversed format.

Validity and Reliability

The developer tested the reliability of the scale using test-retest, and reported internal consistency of .93. For the criterion validity, El-Bassel et al. (1997) correlated DAST-28 with MAST and reported ($r = .59$). The reliability coefficient of DAST was also tested for this study and a Cronbach's Alpha of .85 was reported indicating that the instrument is a reliable tool.

Procedure

Approval for this study was granted by the University, through the Committee on war against substance abuse and trafficking on Campus of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. After which, the researchers randomly selected four Faculties from the nine faculties in the permanent site of the University; they are, Bio Sciences, Education, Social sciences, and Management Sciences. After the faculties were selected using simple random sampling method, purposive sampling method (based on the inclusion criteria) was used in selecting 100 participants from each of the selected faculties that were administered the copies of the questionnaire (DAST, and CAPSAQ); making the total administered questionnaires 400 copies. Of the 400 copies of the administered questionnaires, 397 copies were return, and 394 properly filled copies were selected.

Three copies were invalid on the bases that some items were skipped. The 394 properly filled copies were coded in the SPSS, and were used for data analyses

Inclusion criteria

1. Participant must be either a staff, or student from any of the selected faculties in the University.
2. Participant must be willing to participate in the study by signing a consent form.
3. Participant must be up to 18 years old

Statistics

This research was a cross-sectional survey; while descriptive (percentage), and two-way ANOVA statistics was adapted for data analysis, using SPSS version 25. Data from DAST was used to answer questions number 1, 2, 3, 6, and 7; while CAPSAQ was used to answer questions number 4, and 5

Results

Table 1: Shows in percentage, the total participants, gender, and status (staff or student) of those that abuses drug, those that are likely to be abusing, and non-abusers.

Participants	DAST	N	Percent
Total participants	Drug abusers	20	5.1%
	Likely abusers	62	15.7%
	Non-abusers	312	79.2%
	Total	394	100%
Male	Drug abusers	12	6%
	Likely abusers	32	16%
	Non-abusers	157	78%
	Total	201	100%
Female	Drug abusers	10	5.2%
	Likely abusers	30	15.5%
	Non-abusers	153	79%

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	Total	193	100%
Staff	Drug abusers	4	3.4%
	Likely abusers	10	8.6%
	Non-abusers	102	87.9%
	Total	116	100%
Students	Drug abusers	17	6.1%
	Likely abusers	53	19%
	Non-abusers	208	74.8 %
	Total	278	100%

Table 1 above indicated that from the 394 participants in this study, 20 (5.1%) abuses drug, 62 (15.7%) are likely to be abusing drug; while 312 (79.2%) are non-abusers. It was also found from Table 1 that of the 394 participants, 201 were male, while 193 were female. Among the male participants, 12 (6%) abuses drug, 32 (16%) are likely to be abusing drug; while 157 (78%) are non-abusers. Of the female participants, 10 (5.2%) abuses drug, 30 (15.5%) were likely to be abusing, while 153 (79%) were non-abusers. Furthermore, Table 1 also revealed that of the 394 participants, 116 were staff of the University, while 278 were students. Of the staff participants, 4 (3.4%) abuses drug, 10 (8.6%) were likely to be abusing, while 102 (87.9%) were non-abusers; while among the students participants, 17 (6.1%) abuses drug, 53 (19%) were likely to be abusing drug, while 208 (74.8%) were non-abusers.

Table 2: Shows in percentage, participants' level of awareness on harm caused by psychoactive substance abuse.

Gender	CAPSAQ	N	Percent
Male	Well informed	163	81%
	Limited information	24	11.9%
	Very limited information	14	6.9 %
	Total	201	100%
Female	Well informed	120	62.2%
	Limited information	48	24.8%
	Very limited information	25	12.9 %

Total **193** **100%**

From table 2 above, it was found that among the 394 participants in the study, 201 were male, while 193 were female. Of the male participants, 163 (81%) were well informed of the harm caused by psychoactive substance, 24 (11.9%) had limited information; while 14 (6.9%) had very limited information on harm caused by psychoactive substance abuse. Among the female participants, 120(62%) were well informed, 48(24.8%) had limited information, while 25(12.9%) had very limited information on harm caused by psychoactive substance abuse.

Table 3: Shows in percentage, the rating of participants on drug peddling on Campus.

<i>CAPSAQ</i>	Status	N	Percent
Drug peddlers	Staff	55	13.9%
	Students	133	33.8%
	Outsiders	206	52.3 %
	Total	394	100%

Table 3 showed that of the 394 participants in this study, 55 (13.9%) rated staff involvement in drug peddling, 133 (33.8%) rated students' involvement in drug peddling, while 206 (52.3%) rated that drug peddler around the University community are outsiders'.

Table 4: Shows Factorial ANOVA Results for Gender and Status, on Psychoactive Substance Abuse

Variables	Mean square	df	F	P	η^2
Gender	.236	1(390)	.778	.378	.002
Status	1.704	1(390)	5.617	.018	.014

Note, $p < .05$

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The result in Table 4 revealed that there was no significant difference between male and female on psychoactive substance abuse at $F(1,390)=.778, p>.05$. However, a significant difference was found between staff and students on psych active substance abuse at $F(1,390)=5.617, p<.05$.

Discussion

This study examined the prevalence of substance abuse in a University community in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. A total of 394 members of the University that were selected through multi-stage sampling method participated in this study, and descriptive statistic (percentile), and ANOVA were adopted for data analyses, using SPSS. Seven research questions were postulated, and answered, using data from the 394 participants in this study. From the data analyses, it was found that a good number of individuals (staff and students) within the University community abuse drug; accounting for over five percent of the total participants, which indicated a significant amount; thus, an incidence that should be frowned upon. This finding is in line with that of Peacock et al., (2018) that reported global consumption of illicit drugs as over three percent. Olawole-Isaac et al., (2018), reported the prevalence of substance abuse in Sub-Saharan region as over forty one percent, in Central Africa as over fifty five percent, East Africa as over forty eight percent, while the rate of substance abuse was rated as over thirty eight percent for West Africans. More so, among university populations, Mavhandu-Mudzusi and Asgedom (2016) reported psychoactive substance abuse among undergraduates in Ethiopia as ranging from over sixteen percent to seventy two percent.

For gender prevalence, it was observed that six percent of male participants abuses drug; while over five percent of the female participants abuse drug. The closeness in this gender prevalence indicated that psychoactive substance abuse is not a gender specific problem as both genders were

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found to be involved in psychoactive substance abuse. The inferential analysis conducted using ANOVA statistics further validated the forgoing assertion (psychoactive substance abuse is not gender specific) as no significant difference was found between male and female on psychoactive substance abuse.

Among the staff and student participants, the staff that abuses drug were found to be over three percent of the total staff participants; while among the students participants, over six percent abuses drug. Inferring from the differences in rate of staff and students substance abuse, the prevalence of substance abuse is more among students compare to staff. The inferential analysis that was conducted, using ANOVA statistics further revealed that there was a significant difference between staff and student on psychoactive substance abuse.

The participants' level of awareness on harm caused by substance abuse was also investigated among the male and female participants, and it was found that eighty one percent of the male participants, and sixty two percent of the female participants were well informed on harm caused by substance abuse. In spite of this high level of awareness, there are still cases of psychoactive substance abuse among the participants. Hence, this validates the self-medication theory of addiction which hold that individuals indulge in substance abuse to relieve the negative symptoms associated with withdrawal. This means that majority of these substance abusers could have developed drug dependency, making deliberate withdrawal or abstinence hard, if not impossible, despite being knowledgeable of the risk associated with continues use.

In this study, possible drug markets responsibility for drug distribution within the University community was investigated, and it was reported that over thirteen percent of the peddlers may after all be staff of the University. Student involvement was rated over thirty three percent, while

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over fifty two percent were felt to be outsiders. Thus, accounting for the availability of psychoactive substances within the University community. This availability of psychoactive substance serves as cues that stimulates the desire to use, making abstinence more difficult.

Implications of the Study

This study investigated the prevalence of substance abuse in a University community. From the findings of this study, some implications were highlighted.

1. That there are incidence of substance abuse, involving staff and students in the University, in spite their knowledge of harm caused by such psychoactive substance. Thus, the findings could be used to further elaborate the theoretical framework of this study by empirically showing the presence of substance abuse among people that are knowledgeable on the negative impact of drug they abuse; which could be the resultant their craving that is being complicated by the availability of the abused drug of choice.
2. Since there are incidence of substance abuse in the University, despite the knowledge of harm caused by those drugs, it implies that school management need to be proactive in identifying, and curbing risk factors of substance abuse in the Universities which includes availability of drugs
3. There is urgent need for the establishment of drug policies that will cut down drug availability and in the University.

Recommendations

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From the finding from this study, the researchers recommended as follows:

1. The school management should step up on outreach activities on the implications of substance abuse, and distribution around the Campus.
2. The University management should use the data of this study as evidence to step up on the University drug policies and its enforcement
3. The identification and treatment of already involved persons should be stepped up.

Limitations of the Study

It should be noted that the participants of this study comprised of staff and students of a particular University; as such, could vary from what is observable in other tertiary institution. Hence, generalization of the findings should be made with caution. Furthermore, this study utilized questionnaire (survey) as a mode of data collection which has potential social desirability bias. Thus, would negatively affecting the outcome of this study. However, the researchers assured the participants of the confidentiality of their personal information as well as the exclusion of such information during data collection. Hence, such precaution was aimed at reducing such bias, and enhance their transparency while responding to the questionnaires

Conclusion

This study examined the prevalence of substance abuse among staff and students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka; as well as their level of knowledge on the negative impacts of substance abuse, and their involvement in drug peddling within the University. Seven research questions were postulated, and answered, using data from the descriptive, and two-way ANOVA statistic which revealed that a good number of staff and student were highly involved in substance abuse,

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and its' distribution within the University; despite their level of awareness on the negative impact of psychoactive substances abuse.

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